

The Challenges of Religion and Ethnicity on National Integration in Nigeria

Terna Afella Ph. D

Department of Religion and Cultural Studies, Benue State University, Makurdi

Kpamor Michael Sati

Department of Religion and Cultural Studies, Benue State University, Makurdi

Abstract

Religion and ethnicity have over the years posed great challenges to national integration in Nigeria. Nigeria has experienced several religious crises that have led to destruction of many lives and properties. For instance, ethnicity has taken a centre stage such that one gets what is due for another person simply because of who he knows and where he comes from. This paper tries to examine the challenges posed by religion and ethnicity. The paper adopts a historical approach and the data collected were presented using expository method. It was discovered that this hydra headed monster of religion and ethnicity are the bane of national integration in Nigeria. The paper therefore suggests that, leaders should avoid religious bigotry and ethnic chauvinism; they should stay clear of sponsoring religious activities. Government appointments should not be given based on where a person comes from, but on competence and qualification. Also, politicians should stop mobilizing people for elections based on tribal sentiments but should strive to have popularity across ethnic groups.

Keywords: Religion, Ethnicity, National integration.

Introduction

The negative roles religion and ethnicity have played in Nigeria is so glaring such that those who have eyes can see, and those with ears can hear and those with hands can feel. Religion and ethnicity are supposed to ensure stability for sustainable development to take place through instilling good moral conduct, allegiance to tribe and nation and provision of hope for the people. However, this has not been the case in Nigeria as 90 percent of crises in the country have been linked to the duo. The question therefore is that does the tenet of both religion and ethnicity call for violence? Or better still, is something fundamentally wrong with the tenets of both religion and ethnicity in Nigeria? These and other issues will be the focus of this paper.

Religion

The concept Religion is not easy to define as there is no definition that is generally accepted among religious scholars. The study of religion involves many religious traditions and perspectives like the sociological, psychological, historical, theological, phenomenological, and comparative approaches. These approaches further pose the problem of providing a wholistic view of what constitutes religion. The above is coupled with the science of religion in which empirical and scientific methods are used. Modern scholars are calling for explicit theories, valid definitions, explanations, and understanding of religion to concretize its scientific nature.

However, religion generally denotes man's experience, awareness, attitude, recognition, conception, and understanding of the existence of the supernatural or the explicit of spiritual beings and his relationship with them. It has to do with, not only the beliefs but also, the practice of society based on divine revelation and their corresponding response to the holy. According to A. C. Bonquet, "Religion is a fixed relationship between the human self and some non- human entity, the sacred, the supernatural, the self- existent, the absolute or simply God. Religion is a relationship established between man and transcendent personal being; a deity believed to be in existence."¹

Ethnicity

Ethnicity has its origin from the Greek word *ethnos*, which means ‘band’, ‘group’ or ‘swarm’. Ethnicity definition is no easy to come by. The concept arose from *ethnic*, a word initially applied as social equivalent to race. It was viewed in the 19th century as a derogatory term because it indicated a group as unworthy compared to the mainstream culture. Attempts will however be made to define ethnicity. Ethnicity is defined as a people grouped according to their ethnic groups or characteristics, this can be according to language, culture, tradition, custom, religious beliefs and materials and non-materials things. In other words, it is fundamentally associated with a group shared identity of culture, religion, language, nationality and common ancestry. It can be said to be an embodiment of shared cultural history that gave rise to common world view, ideals and values.²

It is a source of purpose and meaning to live for many individuals who accept its identity based on their membership with the collective group and participation in the tradition of that group fundamental of which is shared language and religion. According to O. Otite, ethnicity is the contextual discrimination by members of one group against the others on the basis of the different system of socio-cultural symbols.³ Ethnicity applies to the consciousness of belonging to, identifying with, and been loyal to social group distinguished by shared cultural traditions, a common language, inter-group sentiment and self-identity.⁴ Ethnicity has the properties of common group consciousness and identity, and also group exclusiveness on the basis of which social discriminations are made. Ethnicity simply means that members of a group are proud and are looking inward.

Ethnicity acquires passionate and aggressive attributes when certain new elements enter in a relationship. These include socio-economic and political competition, fear of domination and closer group interactions fostered by the logic of urbanization and internal migration. Political competition and rivalry seem to be the most inflammable instrument of ethnic aggression. The critical factor in ethnicity is the competition for scarce national resources valued by members in a plural society. Ethnicity therefore starts as an accommodating feeling and later becomes instigated and propelled as a weapon of hostility, conflict and bitter tension.⁵ Thus ethnicism is the situation where ethnicity becomes passionate and aggressive involving conflict and confrontation. In summary, it relates to culturally contingent features, characterizes all human groups. It is a sense of identity and membership in a group that shares common language, cultural traits (values, beliefs, religion, food, habits, custom, etc.) and a sense of common history.

Integration

Integration can generally be said to be a process of fitting into, blending with or becoming a part of a group and or community. It is a process that makes one to possess the traits that makes him or her identify with a group. Various scholars have attempted to define integration; however, that of Awa captures it better. For Awa, “Integration is a process whereby national consciousness, uniqueness of identity and loyalty among people belonging to diverse socio-cultural backgrounds of race, language, religion and ethnic background etc. unify into a single territorial political society.”⁶

Ethnicity in Nigeria

Ethnicity in Nigeria has been traced to the pattern, nature and character of colonial imperialism.⁷ In creating Nigeria, the colonialists amalgamated different groups without giving them a common political orientation. So, despite the amalgamation of 1914, the regions still retained their ethnic or regional identities. It was as a result of this that, the first political parties formed during the colonial era were regionalized based on ethnic identities. The Nation Council of Nigeria and Cameroun, NCNC, formed in 1944 was a national party, but later with the information of the other regional parties it was reduced to the southeastern region. The Northern People’s Congress (NPC) formed in 1949 was for the northern region thus a transformation from the cultural ‘*Jamiyar Murtani Arewa*’. Action Group (AG), formed in 1951 was identified with the western region, transformed from the ‘Egbe Omo Oduduwa’ there were some other political parties formed by the minority groups

in the north like, the United Middle Belt Congress (UMBC) and others, however, they were suppressed by NPC later.

After independence in 1960, the problem of ethnicity became so pronounced such that states were created in order to address the complaints and grievances from the minority groups, since then, more and more states have been created and now we have 36 states. But state creation has even compounded the issue as they gave rise to more agitations. As a result of this, the nation nearly disintegrated as a result of the civil war of 1967 to 1970. Ethnicity has been perceived in general as the major obstacle to the overall Politico- economic development of the country. It is also the propelling factor for the call for sovereign national conference to solve the cries about marginalization. It is also strongly argued that ethnic problem in Nigeria is behind the national question around which a great deal of our national life revolves, and in the name of which all sorts of crimes have been perpetuated against the nation.

Challenges of Religion and Ethnicity on National Integration

National integration is not merely desirable, it is necessary. It will not solve all the problems but none of the major problems can be solved without it. Integration will empower the ordinary people and create the political conditions for much development projects to take off, Ake in Ghana⁸. The democracy is being threatened by ethnic conflicts and antagonism. The nation was ruled by the military for so many years as they thwarted various attempts to democratize, but at last, democracy was restored in 1999. This is now at the mercy of ethnicity as the different ethnic groups struggle to control the scarce resources. As a result of this, we have witnessed several ethnic conflicts all over the country in the past few years. Anugwon and Ibo lamented that if there was a need for a befitting epitaph for the year 2001 in Nigeria it should read 'the year of pronounced bloody inter- ethnic strife.'⁹ There were so many ethno- religious conflicts in that year e. g. the Ife - Modakeke crises in South West, Ijaw- Itsekiri conflicts in the South- South, ethnic crises in Jos, the Tiv-Jukun conflict in Benue and Taraba, Tiv Alago in Benue and Nasarawa States etc.

Ethnicity has taken another dimension in Nigeria; there is the agitation for resource control by the Niger Delta inhabitants i. e. South- south states. Being the oil producing states, they want to have control over it. They have formed association and movement causing a lot of havoc to the economy manifesting in forms of oil theft and pipeline vandalism. This was seen in the concern for power shift in Nigeria politics; were Ibos contested that power should be shifted to the east at the federal level with a candidate from Ibo extraction Peter Obi who co with minority groups agitating for rights to be allowed to govern their states for example the Idoma of Benue State. All these are mounting tension on the government and the citizens alike, so how can democracy thrive in a crisis-ridden situation like this?

Democracy cannot thrive in crises situation because all the efforts and resources of the nation are directed towards conflict resolution to the detriment of developmental projects. The rights and safety of citizens in crises areas is also not guaranteed which is against the tenets of democracy. In areas where the conflicts are between the government and the ethnic groups, they criticize the government and all their efforts are directed towards destabilizing the government. In order to ensure to the welfare of the entire citizenry, the government directs its attention to the crises area neglecting other ones. Other groups that want to be in power also criticize unnecessarily and make the state ungovernable for leaders who do not function effectively as a result of attacks.

Various Ethno- Religious conflicts and antagonisms that have characterized Nigerian politics have a basis in the prevailing capitalist mode of production and distribution. The allocation of resources in the country have been politicized, minority groups complain of marginalization and point to preemption of developmental projects by one or the other ethnic group. All these have tended to create an environment conducive for inter-ethnic competition and rivalry. In a situation characterized by scarcity of resources, the scramble for them among the various ethnic groups have had to be very intense, and a source of conflict of a kind that has threatened political stability and militated against the achievement of national integration.

Religion and Ethnicity in Nigeria

Religion and Ethnicity have influenced the lives of Nigerians in several ways. One importance of religion in Nigeria lies in its use as a tool for education. Both Christianity and Islam came to liberate Nigerians from the shackles of ignorance. Missionaries that introduced both religions taught the people how to read and write so that they could read the holy books. Both Arabic and English in which the Bible and Qur'an were written became the languages most Nigerians learnt to speak and write. Apart from this, the Bible became translated into several languages such as Igbo, Yoruba, Hausa and Tiv which the people learnt to read. These missionaries also, later established schools for the purpose of educating the people: though their main reason was for evangelism. The schools raised consciousness in the youths who acquired them to begin to know their rights and fight for political independence. The people so trained served as human resources in various sectors to propel development in the nation. The continuous intervention of these religious bodies in the area of establishments of schools for lower and higher certificates is commendable. They establish schools to care for the handicap in the society for example the school for the deaf and dumb in Vandeikya, Benue State Nigeria.

In the health sector too they did so much, they offered prayers for people which healed many of their diseases and helped in the area of spiritual attacks. They also established health centers and hospitals such as Mkar Christian Hospital, Mkar, NKST Hospital Lessel, St. Thomas Hospital Ihugh and Mkar Christian Hospital in Benue, and others across Nigeria. These hospitals provided health care to the people as diseases that could not be properly handled by the traditional medical practitioners such as leprosy, polio, tuberculosis, eyes problems were cured at these hospitals. Economically, they brought economic plants such as Mangoes, Oranges, and Soya Beans, Beans which the people planted and sold and made money. A side from this, the Schools, Hospitals, Health and worship center's they built provided jobs for people. African Religious healers also practiced their profession and made a living through it.

Religious organizations also ended bad practices in Nigeria such as the killing of twins, cripples, and cannibalism in some communities. They ensured peaceful co- existence through inter- religious bodies they formed. These religious councils have intervened and resolved several religious crises mostly between Christians and Muslims even in recent times.

If all ethnic groups will view their unique cultures as spices of life, healthy competition rather than call to rivalry, there won't be bickering. Therefore, it behooves of Nigerians to show case their ethnic and cultural practices and its beauty just for people to appreciate it. The country is blessed with legions of ethnic groups and each of these groups has wonderful cultural practices to show case to the world for tourist attraction. This can make the nation improve its economy as the tourist will bring in their monies to hire hotels, feed as well as make purchase of goods in Nigeria. If the various ethnic groups show case their cultural practices and this attracts foreign tourists who would come to enjoy the rich culture of the Nigerian peoples, the nation will be better for it. Therefore, ethnic groups in Nigeria instead of promotion of primordial sentiments should rather focus on use of their diversity for tourist attraction; after all it is said, "there is strength in unity" and also that, "a house divided against itself cannot stand". In other words, the diversity in ethnicity should be for strength and development and not for weakness and destruction.

Abuse of Religion and Ethnicity in Nigeria

Religion has been greatly abused in Nigeria. Some practices of the Traditional Religion have led to sacrifice of human beings for example the *ioor* and *Imborivungu* of the Tiv, *inikpi* among Igala. People have been killed in the name of a god declaring them as evil and many others offered as sacrifice to a god for example the Okija shrine saga in Anambra State in Nigeria where corpses were found around the shrine and the priest arrested said they were people sacrificed for various reasons. These practices also exist among other ethnic groups across the nation.

Christianity and Islam have been the most abused religions in recent years. They have been used by their adherents as weapons for settling problems and for pressing for political rights. This is so because Nigeria is

divided vice versa and each group is always suspicious that one is trying to dominate the other. Thus, Christians and Muslims have been involved in crises that have led to death of several people and destruction of properties worth millions of naira. Poverty and lack of jobs has turned many to religion for survival. Religious leaders have commercialized religion extorting money from unsuspecting congregational members. A 'Pentecostal' preacher as most of the Churches cropping up in recent times are referred to while preaching said "God hates the noise of coins." This was when coins were still in use in Nigeria. He said this to motivate his members to give naira notes that were in higher denominations rather than give offering with coins that were in very low denominations.

Also, preachers tell their members to 'lay their treasures in heaven' or that 'God loves a cheerful giver'. By this they mean as one gives much to the Church, he or she is investing to his or her account in heaven and will receive Gods favour on the Judgement Day. The proliferation of Churches, the faking of miracles and involvement of preachers in occult practices is all aimed at getting many members. And the larger the congregation one has the more money he or she make during offering. Some preachers have taken to visiting the rich in their homes to pray for them so as to get money. Members of the public are not left out in this as some of them who sometimes are physically healthy engage in street begging using religion as their base for example the Muslim *almajiri* practice.

In Nigeria, preachers who preach inciting messages that will prompt t people to fight earn more of the people's confidence and respect. It is on record that most religious crisis in Northern Nigeria occurred on Friday after Jumat Prayers (Muslim Worship Day). After being incited in the course of worship by the imam, the worshippers rushed out chanting "*Allahu akbar!*" meaning "God is Great," chanting this, they attacked their enemies who were usually Christians killing them and destroying their properties. This is strange because worship centres are supposed to be places people will receive good moral teaching that will make them to be peaceful. Even if aggrieved, they should be calmed down by their preachers and not to be instigated as the case in Nigeria. Medicine men and priests tell their unsuspecting client's fabulous stories about witches or wicked relations that are bewitching them in order to extort money from them with fake solutions.

Ethnicity on the other hand has also been abused in several ways, for example it is often misused as a tool for ethnic mobilization to champion selfish cause. Nigerian political parties have always had ethnic or religious colouration. For example, in the first republic we had NPC for the Northern Nigeria, the United Middle Belt Congress (UMBC) for the Middle Belt in and the Action Group (AG) for the Western Nigeria and National Council for Nigeria Citizens (NCNC) for the Eastern Nigeria¹⁰. This has been the reason for its easy manipulation by selfish politicians who do not have the ability to persuade electorates by the use of persuasive language but rather use sentiments such as "the other Regions are marginalizing us so let us fight for our rights", this they do to gain support from their people. Political parties in Nigeria are often not formed based on sound principles and ideologies. Thus, politicians do not stick to an ideology they play the politics of convenience and self-aggrandizement which explains why politicians keep cross carpeting from one political party to another when their former party is out of government or when they are denied a political post.

Political leaders promote hatred, violence, intimidation, and murder of political opponents. There have been political tussles or crises in different parts of the country which led to deaths of politicians such as Chief Bole Ige, Harry Marshal, Ezekiel Akiga, Andrew Agom, Chief Dikkibo and many others. Most times, elections are not conducted in some places but people declared as winners with vote caste higher than the total population of people registered by Independent National Electoral Commission. Those that emerged engage in un-democratic practices. Their leadership is characterized by gross abuse of power. Decisions are taken and executed by leaders without due process because they have not been voted to power and are therefore not accountable to anybody. When they are criticized, they appeal to their ethnic group to rise up in their defense; claiming that it is because they belong to their group that others are criticizing them. Thus, in Nigeria, when a public servant misbehaves and is been held accountable, his people ignore the crime and rise up in his defense claiming it is because he belongs to a particular ethnic group that he is being persecuted. For example, if an Ibo man embezzles public funds and is arrested, the Ibos rise to his defense, so also the Tiv, Hausa, Yoruba etc.

The worst part is people supporting candidates from their ethnic nationality even when they know that such a candidate cannot deliver. In the current political dispensation, Nigerians support candidates based on ethnic and religious inclinations. When a northerner is contesting against a southerner, more of northerners support the northern candidate while the southerners support the southerner. This also goes according to religious inclination as more of Muslims will vote a Muslim candidate and more of Christians will vote a Christian candidate. In the last elections the key contestants in the presidential elections were Bola Tinubu from the south, Atiku Abubakar from the North and Peter Obi from the East. It is possible to say that, Tinubu had more support from the west, while Atiku had from the North and Obi from the East.

Consequences of Religio–Ethnic Crisis on National Integrations

Religio-political crisis has a very long history in Nigeria. The nature and dimensions of these crises takes different forms and patterns of occurrence. The manifestations of this crisis have often been violent and threatening to the corporate existence of Nigeria as a nation state. The conditions created have also hampered the wealth, transformation and progress of Nigeria in many ways. It has led to the stagnation of the country's development at all fronts. Following the trend of occurrence and perpetration, it may be strongly believed that the situation has serious social, economic, political and psychological consequences, pathological to the existence of the country as a functional democratic state.¹¹

Anugwon and Ibo therefore maintain that, the social implication refers to the disorderliness of the civil society, the phenomenon generated at each point of incidence in terms of spread and perpetuity. The scenario created by the rapid rate of religious upheavals in Nigeria today seems to question the rationale for the continued co-existence of the diverse ethnic nationalities that make up the country.¹² The extent to this experience questions the relevance of the continued slogan of “unity in diversity” the patriotic citizens of this country still labour to uphold. Some Christian-Igbo, Yoruba and Tiv etc. are also suspicious of the Hausa/Fulani of Muslims extraction in their inter-relationship with one another. There can hardly be any meaningful and functional interaction among these ethno-religious groups because there is that feeling of insecurity amongst them that makes constructive relationship impossible. This is because, religio- political crises have led to the destruction of life- time investments or business outfits, crops and government establishments. This has led many people who were rich to become poor persons who can now hardly provide food for their families.

Also, religio-ethnic crisis has made infrastructural development in Nigeria to be so difficult. In many cases the money that would have been channeled by government to developmental projects is used to boost security in crisis, rehabilitate victims of crises as well as for relief materials to the victims. This leads to serious consequences on the economy thus leading to high cost of living.¹³ Religio-ethnic crisis often renders people homeless and without a means of self- sustenance. This leads to poverty in the land especially where people's investments are destroyed and the resources meant for developmental projects to create jobs are channeled towards security. This is seriously hindering national integration.

Religio-ethnic crises result to wanton destruction of properties. During most crises, people target important public structures such as police stations, churches, mosques, government offices and private residential houses and businesses. The destruction of such buildings results to serious set- back in the places they were established. Some of such structures are never replaced again by the government or their owners. Religio-ethnic crisis has led to deaths of uncountable human resources that would have served as man- power that would help the nation to bring about national integration. In Nigeria today, it is difficult for one to give the actual number of people killed in crises in Nigeria because the crisis has been too frequent.

Religio-ethnic crises have portrayed the nation in bad light before the community of nations thus discouraging foreign investors from coming to Nigeria to invest in order to grow the nation's economy. This has denied the nation sustainable development as no man desires to come and invest where there is crisis for fear of its destruction. Furthermore, it has also discouraged indigenes from also investing in the nation in fear that crises

may destroy their investments they rather invest in other countries and this has affected sustainable development in Nigeria.

Religio-ethnic crisis has led to mass movement of Nigerians who would have salvaged their country or their localities to foreign lands or other places that are safe for fear of being killed in crises areas this has affected the nations sustainable development. Today we have Nigerians moving to other states down south of Nigeria and even to other countries such as Niger Republic and Togo for fear of being victims of Boko Haram insurgents. Religio- ethnic crises have disrupted good governance in Nigeria. When the crisis is on the attention of leaders are divided. They are caught between provision of amenities for the people as well as channeling resources to law enforcement agencies such as the police or even the military forces to quell the crisis. The leader becomes restless and on pressure to end the crisis because it portrays the government or administration in bad lights.

Religio-ethnic crises have led to most rural communities in Tiv and Idoma areas been plundered by Fulani militia who bring their cows to feed on people's farms and when they complain, they are brutally attacked. This has resulted to people been sacked from their communities and are house in refugee camps. Any attempt by them to return to their ancestral homes is resisted by the militia who lay ambush and kill them. These challenges are also experienced by other communities in the North and south of Nigeria. For others, it is cattle rustling by bandits.

Conclusion

Religion and ethnicity should serve as tools for promoting peace, progress, and integration in Nigeria rather than the disunity the adherents are promoting today. Through the development of morally up- right people who are just and sincere in governance and other forms of dealings for the progress of the society. Religion should assist people to cultivate the virtues of love for one's neighbours and shun every form of evil and wickedness while religio-ethnic practices should bring development.

Different ethnic groups in Nigeria have rich cultures that if properly harnessed for tourism will give foreign earning to the country which can be used for development. Therefore, rather than use our differences of religio-ethnic practices for destroying one another, we should take advantage of it for proper integration which will ultimately lead to development of the nation. This will bring peaceful co- existence that will result to prosperity bequeathed to the next generation.

Recommendations

Nigerians should accept the differences of religion and ethnicity as the beauty of God's creation. They should explore ways of using the diversity for development rather than destruction. God in His infinite wisdom has created people with different ethno- religious practices to His glory. If humans will learn to integrate, they will experience great harmony and progress. Religion should not be meddled with politics and religious activities should not be sponsored by government in accordance to the constitutional provision. Government should declare free education for the youths and more schools should be built to accommodate the teeming population of the youths in the nation.

Government should provide a conducive environment for private investors through good policies and peaceful atmosphere so that industries will be set- up to create job opportunities for the youths because government is not a good manager of business outfits. Government should engage in infrastructural development by providing good roads, hospitals, clinics, electricity, recreational centres, housing estates etc. to ease life for the people. Government should stop meddling in religious activities. Politicking should always give way for good governance once elections have been conducted and people are elected. Religious leaders should focus on preaching morality rather than prosperity as is done today so that good citizens and leaders will be raised to provide sustainable development.

Nigerians should learn to live in peace with one another other and accommodate their differences. No Nigerian should compel another to practice his religion. Everyone should be allowed to associate with any lawful group he or she wishes to associate with. Though government has tried by declaring state of emergency in states

besieged by Boko Haram insurgents and by the amnesty offered to the insurgents, it can still do more by taking the youths off the streets engaging them in useful ventures such as training them in various skill acquisition programs of their choices and providing them with loans to set up business outfits. Give those who wish to acquire education the chance to have free education. Also, there is need to address the issues of hunger, poverty and marginalization's of groups or regions in the country which are often reasons given for these up-risings. Miscreants found to be bent on destabilizing the nation should be punished in accordance with the Law.

The military should not be biased in handling cases of religio-ethnic crises as it currently been accused of. In many places there are these crises, the military personnel sent to quell the situation are accused of taking sides with one ethnic group by shielding it to attack the other. This is bad, because the military is supposed to be neutral. Their mandate is to protect lives and properties of citizens irrespective of their religion and ethnic lineage. Government should cease from using public funds to support one group against the other through supply of arms, money or materials. Leaders should see Nigeria as their constituency. They should not align to their faith or ethnic group to the detriment of others. Nigerians should be encouraged by the ministry of culture and tourism to use the difference in religious and cultural practices to attract tourists. Most of the groups in Nigeria have great cultural practices that if harnessed, will make Nigeria one of the greatest tourist centres in the world.

Endnotes

¹A. C. Bouquet, "Comparative Religion" In *Social Injustice, the Challenge to Religion in Nigeria*. Agule T. C. Ed. (Makurdi. Traces Publishers, 2006), 168.

²A. Dzurgba, *Principles of Ethics* (Ibadan: Agape Publication 2000), 22.

³O. Otite, *Ethnic Pluralism and Ethnicity in Nigeria* (Ibadan: Shaneson limited, 1990), 17.

⁴F. Omu, "Ethnicity, National and Federalism," in *Foundations of Nigerian Federalism 1900 to 1960*. Isawa E. and Uzoigwe G. N. eds. Abuja: National Council of Intergovernmental Relations (1995), 36.

⁶O. Otite, *Ethnic Pluralism and Ethnicity in Nigeria* (Ibadan: Shaneson Limited, 1990), 37.

⁷G. Awa, *Ethics and Ethical Values for National Development in the 21st Century*. Tutorial press Ltd, slough, 2008.

⁸O. O. Okpoh, "The Sovereign National Conference: A Historical Appraisal of Contending Issues and their Implication for the Corporeality of the Nigeria Nation," in *The Sovereign National Conference*. Okpoh, O. O. ed. Makurdi: Aboki Publishers, 2003.

⁹A. T. Gana, "Civil Society and the Consolidation of Democracy," in *Nigerian Journal of Political and Administrative Studies*, Vol. 1 No. 2. Makurdi: Aboki Publishers.

¹⁰Anugwon and P. Ibo, *Social Change and Social Problems: A Nigerian Experience*, Nsukka (Nigeria: A. P. Express Pub. 2002), 27.

¹¹T. Abeghe. *Tiv Riots and the Aftermaths* (Makurdi: Oracle Business Limited, 2005).

¹²C. Achebe, *The Trouble with Nigeria* (Enugu: Fourth Dimension Publishing Company Limited), 1993.

¹³Anugwon and Ibo, 27.

¹⁴T. Afella. "An Overview of Political Crises and the Implications for Political Stability in Tivland: The Role of Ator a Tiv," in *Issues and Perspectives in Tiv Politics and National Development*, Orgu, C. and Wuam, T. Eds.